

Comparative Analysis of Complete Demagnetization in Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Topologies

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Abstract—This paper examines the effects of local irreversible demagnetization faults, applied to one pole and two poles, on the performance of three topologies of Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs): Surface-mounted Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SPMSM), Inset Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (IPMSM), and Spoke-Interior Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (SIPMSM). The analysis focuses on cogging torque, electromagnetic torque, back-induced electromotive force (back-induced EMF), and magnetic flux density in the air gap for healthy and locally demagnetized permanent magnets. The results provide valuable insights into the considerations necessary for advancing online condition monitoring systems aimed at the early detection and mitigation of permanent magnets issues and the identification of the affected magnets.

Index Terms—local irreversible demagnetization, Fast Fourier Transform, cogging torque, fault detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

The permanent magnet synchronous motors (PMSMs) are extensively used across various industrial applications due to their high efficiency, high power density and high torque density [1], [2]. However, the performance of PMSMs is reduced by the faults, including demagnetization faults [3]. Demagnetization faults can be classified as either reversible or irreversible [4]. Reversible demagnetization appears when a magnet experiences a reduction in its magnetic field strength due to external influence and recovers its magnetic field strength after the removal of these external factors, the magnet can return to its original magnetic characteristics without the necessity for re-magnetization. But irreversible demagnetization refers to the permanent loss of magnetic field strength in a magnet that can't be regained. This phenomenon occurs when the magnet is subjected to external conditions that exceed its intrinsic capacity [5].

A combination of thermal, electrical, mechanical, and ambient operating stresses are the primary causes of irreversible demagnetization, with elevated operating temperatures and currents serving as the principal contributing factors [6], [7]. Additionally, permanent magnets (PMs) can undergo uniform or partial demagnetization. In instances of uniform demagnetization,

all magnets experience simultaneous demagnetization to an identical degree. Conversely, in cases of partial demagnetization, only a subset of magnets is affected by the defect [3], [8]. Greater than the Curie temperature, thermal condition leads to the irreversible loss of magnetic properties in PMs. The Curie temperatures of SmCo magnet is above 350°C, while NdFeB can work up to 230°C [9]. However, even below the Curie point, both the remanence and intrinsic coercivity of PMs decrease as temperature increases. Consequently, as the temperature rises, the material becomes increasingly susceptible to local demagnetization due to the magnetic field generated by the stator current during normal operation, as well as under conditions of short circuit and overcurrent. During these instances, temperature induces uniform demagnetization of the PMs, while overcurrent results in partial and local demagnetization, with the affected locations influenced by the orientation of the magnetic field produced by the stator current [6]. The assessment of local demagnetization is considerably more challenging due to inherent asymmetry and is particularly influenced by the rotor topology [10].

Local irreversible demagnetization commences at the trailing edge of the rotor pole and progressively propagates over time, potentially affecting the entire pole if the fault is not diagnosed on time, and it can extend to adjacent poles. The main cause of this phenomenon is the q-axis component [11], [12], [13]. The local demagnetization in Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motors (PMSMs) results in an unbalanced back electromotive force (EMF) and unequal phase currents. These phenomena contribute to excessive current in the stator windings, thereby increasing copper losses, inducing greater torque ripple, and causing an imbalance in the electromagnetic flux density within the air gap [12]. This comparative study examines local demagnetization detection in one-pole and two-pole configurations across three different permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM) topologies. The results contribute to the understanding of the extent of demagnetization present in each topology.

The structure of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the studied PMSM topologies and their associated theoretical considerations. Section III examines the implementation of local demagnetization. Section IV is dedicated to the simulation results and discussion of the local

demagnetization fault. Section V provides a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis of induced EMF and cogging torque. Finally, Section VI presents the conclusions of the paper.

II. MODELING OF THE PMSM TOPOLOGIES

The topologies examined in this study include the Surface-mounted Synchronous Permanent Magnet Motor (SPMSM), the Inset Synchronous Permanent Magnet Motor (IPMSM), and the Spoke-type Interior Synchronous Permanent Magnet Motor (SIPMSM). Each of these topologies was designed following identical electrical specifications and maintained a constant air-gap diameter in all topologies.

Fig. 1. The rotor topologies and magnetization directions are in orange

The motors are designed according to the electrical and geometrical specifications presented in Table I.

TABLE I. PMSM PARAMETERS

Parameters	Value
Number of pole pairs, p	4
Supply frequency, f	300 Hz
Rated torque	4.671 Nm
DC link	72 volts
Number of slots in the stator	18
Total PM volume	15170 mm ³
Rated speed	4500 RPM
rated power	2200 watts

Fig. 2. Three-phase stator winding layout of studied PMSM: 18 slots double-layer distributed windings

The PMSM topologies for this study are designed with 3-phase, 4 pole pairs and 18 slots. Fig. 2 presents an overview of the configurations of the examined stator windings. The winding is organized into two layers, featuring a coil pitch of 2, a pole pitch of 2.25, and a winding factor of 0.617.

The voltage of the PMSM in the rotor reference frame can be obtained as follows:

$$V_q = R_s i_q + L_q \frac{di_q}{dt} + \omega_r L_d i_d + \omega_r \lambda_m \quad (1)$$

$$V_d = R_s i_d - \omega_r L_q i_q + L_d \frac{di_d}{dt} \quad (2)$$

The flux linkage equations are as follows:

$$\lambda_q = L_q i_q \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_d = L_d i_d + \lambda_f \quad (4)$$

Where:

V_q : Q-axis component of the stator voltage (in volts)

V_d : D-axis component of the stator voltage (in volts)

i_d : Direct-axis component of the stator current (in amperes)

i_q : Quadrature -axis component of the stator current (in amperes)

L_d : d-axis inductance (in henry)

L_q : q-axis inductance (in henry)

ω_r : rotor electrical speed (rad/s)

λ_m : PM flux linkage (in Weber)

λ_q : The flux linkage in the q-axis

λ_d : The flux linkage in the d-axis

R_s : Stator resistance (in ohm)

The electromagnetic torque for PMSM in the direct-quadrature axes can be obtained as follows:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} p (\lambda_m i_q + (L_d - L_q) i_d i_q) \quad (5)$$

Where:

T_e : electromagnetic torque of the PMSM

p : number of pole pairs

As shown in equation (5), the value of the electromagnetic torque for a PMSM is directly related to the PM flux linkage. Therefore, the demagnetization of the permanent magnet directly reduces the electromagnetic torque.

The induced back electromotive force (EMF), $e_{ph}(t)$ for one phase is derived using Faraday's law of induction.

$$e_{ph}(t) = - \frac{d\Psi_{ph}(t)}{dt} \quad (6)$$

The phase flux linkage (Ψ_{ph}) includes the flux linkage from the rotor's permanent magnets and the flux produced by the phase current in the windings over time, t . The induced back-EMF, represented as $e_{ph}(t)$, is affected when the magnetic material becomes demagnetized because the induced back-EMF relies on the rotor's permanent magnet flux linkage. The torque ripple (T_{ripple}) can be calculated as follows:

$$T_{ripple}(\%) = \frac{T_{max} - T_{min}}{T_{av}} \quad (7)$$

Where T_{max} represents the maximum instantaneous torque, T_{min} denotes the minimum instantaneous torque, and T_{av} indicates the average electromagnetic torque.

The air-gap magnetic flux density, B_g of PMSM can be calculated by:

$$B_g = \frac{\mu_0 \mu_r H_m}{1 + \frac{g}{\delta_{pm}}} \quad (8)$$

Where; μ_0 : Vacuum permeability ($4\pi \times 10^{-7} H/m$)
 μ_r : Relative permeability of the permanent magnet (μ_r for NdFeB is 1.05)
 H_m : Magnetic field strength of the magnet (in A/m)
 g : Length of the airgap (in mm)
 δ_{pm} : Thickness of the magnet (in mm)

The efficiency, η of motor can be calculated as:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

P_{out} represents the mechanical power output, and P_{in} denotes the electrical power input. The efficiency of a PMSM varies with changes in iron and copper losses; as these losses increase, the efficiency of the motor correspondingly declines. implementation of local demagnetization

III. LOCAL DEMAGNETIZATION IMPLEMENTATION

This section presents an analysis of local demagnetization phenomena. It has been observed that the trailing edge of motor magnets may undergo local demagnetization due to the orientation of the magnetic field generated by the stator current. The initiation of this local demagnetization fault occurs at the edge of the permanent magnets and progressively propagates over time, potentially impacting the entire pole if the fault is not identified and addressed promptly [11].

The simulation of healthy magnets, one-pole, and two-pole demagnetized magnets within each PMSM rotor topology was conducted using the finite element method (FEM). Complete demagnetization in one-pole and two-pole configurations was modeled by demagnetizing one or two magnets, as shown in Fig. 3, Fig. 4, and Fig. 5. The flux lines indicate the orientation of the magnetic flux density, with a higher density of lines representing a stronger magnetic flux. The demagnetized magnets are shown in violet in Fig. 3, Fig. 4, and Fig. 5. It is clear that the demagnetized magnets or poles do not generate magnetic flux density, as they no longer exhibit the properties of magnetic materials.

Fig. 3. The flux density distribution in the faulty SPMSM: (a) one pole demagnetized; (b) two poles demagnetized.

Fig. 4. The flux density distribution in the faulty inset-type PMSM: (a) one pole demagnetized; (b) two poles demagnetized.

Fig. 5. The flux density distribution in the faulty spoke-type interior PMSM: (a) one pole demagnetized; (b) two poles demagnetized.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF THE LOCAL DEMAGNETIZATION FAULT

The simulation results for each motor topology were obtained under rated conditions, specifically a current of 40.45 A, a frequency of 300 Hz, and a speed of 4500 rpm. The complete demagnetization of both one-pole and two-pole configurations resulted in a reduction of the intrinsic coercive field of the permanent magnet to zero.

The results for the three PMSM topologies are presented in Table II. The table shows the RMS values of the back-induced EMF (RMS EMF), the average value of the electromagnetic torque (T_{av}), and magnetic flux density in the air gap (B_δ), torque ripple (T_{ripple}), and PMSM efficiency (η).

Fig. 6, Fig. 7, and Fig. 8 present the electromagnetic torque characteristics of the PMSM topologies under different conditions. The horizontal lines denote the average electromagnetic torque in each graph, with corresponding values shown within the figures. Additionally, Fig. 9, Fig. 10, and Fig. 11 illustrate the back-induced EMF under different conditions. Fig. 12, Fig. 13, and Fig. 14 provide a FFT analysis of the back-induced EMF, while Fig. 15, Fig. 16, and Fig. 17 present the FFT of the cogging torque.

TABLE II. TORQUE, BACK-EMF, EFFICIENCY, AND MAGNETIC FLUX DENSITY

Parameters		T_{av} (Nm)	RMS EMF (V)	T_{ripple} (%)	B_{δ} (T)	η (%)
PMSM state						
SPMSM	Healthy PM	4.767	27.7	4.93	0.67	93
	One pole Demagnetized	4.171	24.27	17.1	0.62	91.8
	Two poles Demagnetized	3.385	20.98	18.7	0.58	89.8
IPMSM	Healthy PM	4.677	28.2	11.1	0.71	92.8
	One pole Demagnetized	4.104	24.78	23.7	0.67	91.7
	Two poles Demagnetized	3.520	21.38	25.4	0.64	90.4
SIPMSM	Healthy PM	3.866	26.4	13.9	0.68	91.3
	One pole Demagnetized	3.364	22.87	26.2	0.64	90
	Two poles Demagnetized	2.878	19.53	31.2	0.63	88.4

Table II presents the results for healthy and demagnetized permanent magnets with one and two poles for SPMSM, IPMSM, and SIPMSM. The values in Table II indicate that the average electromagnetic torque, RMS value of EMFs, air gap magnetic flux density, and motor efficiency vary due to the effects of the demagnetization fault. The results of pole demagnetization across all topologies demonstrate that this fault significantly impacts the motor's performance, as proven by a decrease in motor efficiency (as shown in Table II). A comparative analysis of average torque indicates that the average torque of the healthy PM is reduced due to pole faults as follows:

- SPMSM: A reduction of 12.51% in one-pole demagnetization (decreasing from 4.767 Nm to 4.104 Nm) and a reduction of 24.79% in two-pole demagnetization (decreasing from 4.767 Nm to 3.385 Nm) was observed.
- IPMSM: A reduction of 12.24% in one-pole demagnetization (decreasing from 4.677 Nm to 4.171 Nm) and a reduction of 24.73% in two-pole demagnetization (decreasing from 4.677 Nm to 3.520 Nm) was observed.
- SIPMSM: A reduction of 12.98% in one-pole demagnetization (decreasing from 3.866 Nm to 3.364 Nm) and a reduction of 25.54% in two-pole demagnetization (decreasing from 3.866 Nm to 2.878 Nm) was observed.

Fig. 6. Comparative results of average electromagnetic torque in SPMSM

Fig. 7. Comparative results of average electromagnetic torque in IPMSM

Fig. 8. Comparative results of average electromagnetic torque in SIPMSM

As shown in Table II and Fig. 9, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, the demagnetization fault in the rotor poles decreases the RMS value of the induced EMF and creates an imbalance in EMF waveforms across all PMSM topologies. In addition, the demagnetization fault affecting the poles reduces the magnetic flux density in the air gap, nearly doubling the torque ripple compared to that of a healthy motor, as indicated in Table II.

The complete demagnetization of the poles causes the motor to run at high speed, as shown in equation 10.

$$N_s = \frac{60f_s}{p} \quad (10)$$

Where:

N_s : Synchronous speed (rpm)

p : Pole pairs

f_s : Supply frequency (in Hertz)

Fig. 9. Induced EMF waveforms in the SPMSM topology: (a) comparison of EMF under healthy and faulty poles; (b) EMF waveforms for each case

Fig. 10. Induced EMF waveforms in the IPMSM topology: (a) comparison of EMF under healthy and faulty poles; (b) EMF waveforms for each case

Fig. 11. Induced EMF waveforms in the SIPMSM topology: (a) comparison of EMF under healthy and faulty poles; (b) EMF waveforms for each case

V. FAST FOURIER TRANSFORM (FFT) ANALYSIS OF INDUCED EMF AND COGGING TORQUE

A. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) Analysis of Back-induced EMF

Fig. 12, Fig. 13, and Fig. 14 illustrate the harmonic contents of back-induced EMF for both healthy and faulty PMSM topologies. Per unit notation is employed to facilitate the comparison of harmonics across all cases. The maximum value of 1 per unit represents the fundamental amplitude of the back-induced EMF in the healthy conditions.

Fig. 12. Harmonic content of back-induced EMF for SPMSM under different conditions

Fig. 13. Harmonic content of back-induced EMF for IPMSM under different conditions

Fig. 14. Harmonic content of back-induced EMF for SIPMSM under different conditions

The FFT analysis of back-induced results in each topology is as follows:

- SPMSM: The analysis indicates that the 0.5th order, 1.5th order, and 3.5th order harmonics are present in this topology during the demagnetization of the north and south poles. These harmonics may act as indicators of a 2-pole demagnetization fault. Conversely, in the case of a 1-pole demagnetization fault, the presence of the 6th and 8th-order harmonics provides a characteristic signature of this specific fault condition (as indicated in Fig. 12).
- IPMSM: Fig. 13 shows that the 0.5th order, 1.5th order, and 3.5th order harmonics are present during the demagnetization of two poles. These harmonics may indicate a 2-pole demagnetization fault. Conversely, in the case of a 1-pole demagnetization fault, the presence of the 4th, 6th, and 8th-order harmonics provides a characteristic signature of this fault condition.
- SIPMSM: Fig. 14 shows that the 0.5th, 1.5th, 3.5th, 5th, 5.5th, and 8th order harmonics are present during the demagnetization fault of two poles. These harmonics may be a signature of a 2-pole demagnetization fault. Conversely, in the case of a 1-pole demagnetization fault, the presence of the 5th and 5th order harmonics provides a characteristic signature of this fault condition.

The presence of the harmonic components serves as the primary indicator of the poles' demagnetization fault. In healthy PM, the harmonic components are zero, making this characteristic useful for monitoring the health of the magnets within the rotor.

B. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) Analysis of Cogging Torque

The demagnetization fault in PMSM can be detected by analyzing the FFT of the cogging torque. The fundamental frequency of the cogging torque is determined by the interaction between the rotor's magnetic poles and the stator slots.
$$f_{\text{cog}} = \frac{N_s N_{\text{slots}}}{60} \quad (11)$$

Where, f_{cog} : The fundamental cogging torque frequency (Hz), N_s : Synchronous speed (RPM), and N_{slots} : Number of slots

Fig. 15. Harmonic content of cogging torque for SPMSM under different conditions

Fig. 16. Harmonic content of cogging torque for IPMSM under different conditions

Fig. 17. Harmonic content of cogging torque for SPMSM under different conditions

Fig. 15, Fig.16, and Fig. 17 depict the harmonic content of cogging torque for both healthy and faulty PMSM topologies. Based on the rated parameters presented in Table I and equation (11), the fundamental frequency of cogging torque is determined to be 1350 Hz. In the case of Surface-Mounted PMSM and Inset PMSM, the amplitudes of the 2nd harmonic (2700 Hz) and the 3rd harmonic (4050 Hz) are found to be higher under one-pole demagnetization compared to two-pole demagnetization fault. Conversely, for the spoke interior PMSM, the amplitudes of the 2nd harmonic (2700 Hz) and the 3rd harmonic (4050 Hz) are observed to be higher under a two-pole demagnetization fault than with one-pole demagnetization. In a 1-pole demagnetization fault, the highest amplitude of the 2nd order harmonic cogging torque occurs in the IPMSM (0.0838 Nm), followed by the SPMSM (0.0639 Nm) and SIPMSM (0.0111 Nm). Similarly, in a 2-pole demagnetization fault, the highest amplitude of the 2nd order harmonic cogging torque is again in the IPMSM (0.03385 Nm), compared to the SPMSM (0.0245 Nm) and

SIPMSM (0.0182 Nm). This scenario is reflected in the third-order harmonic of the cogging torque as follows:

One-pole demagnetization fault: IPMSM (0.0165 Nm), SPMSM (0.0126 Nm), and SIPMSM (0.0022 Nm).

Two-pole demagnetization fault: IPMSM (0.00669 Nm), SPMSM (0.00043 Nm), and SIPMSM (0.0036 Nm).

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that permanent magnets lose their magnetic properties during pole demagnetization. Although all three PMSM topologies are designed under the same constraints, specifically, the volume of magnets, the number of slots, and the air gap diameter, the average electromagnetic torque values differ. The SPMSM achieves an average torque of 4.767 Nm, while the IPMSM achieves 4.677 Nm. Both motors meet the rated torque under healthy permanent magnet conditions, as shown in Table I. In contrast, the average torque for the SIPMSM falls below the rated torque at 3.866 Nm. This difference results from the position and shape of the magnets in each rotor topology. Following the implementation of pole demagnetization, the electromagnetic torque values across all topologies show a decrease, quantified as follows: for one-pole demagnetization, the reductions are 12.51% for SPMSM, 12.24% for IPMSM, and 12.98% for SIPMSM. For two-pole demagnetization, the reductions are 24.79% for SPMSM, 24.73% for IPMSM, and 25.54% for SIPMSM. These results highlight the negative impact of local demagnetization on motor performance.

All topologies experience increased torque ripples, resulting in vibration and noise during operation. Among these, SPMSM is most vulnerable to pole demagnetization, with torque ripple increasing by more than three times (3.48 times for one-pole faults and 3.79 times for two-pole faults) compared to motors with healthy permanent magnets. The IPMSM follows, showing an increase of more than two times (2.13 times for one-pole faults and 2.28 times for two-pole faults). SIPMSM suffers increases of 1.87 times for one-pole faults and 2.23 times for two-pole faults. Additionally, pole demagnetization faults lead to a decrease in the induced back electromotive force (EMF) and magnetic flux density in the air gap. The efficiency of different motor topologies also varies due to differences in motor losses and reduced motor torque.

This research has identified indicators for detecting complete pole demagnetization faults in three PMSM topologies: SPMSM, IPMSM, and SIPMSM. The FFT of the back-induced EMF and cogging torque provides information on this fault. Condition monitoring is essential for early detection and mitigation of demagnetization effects, as this fault causes an imbalance in the air gap magnetic flux density and leads the motor to operate above its rated speed.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the Horizon Europe project Network of Excellence in Digital Technologies and AI Solutions for Electromechanical and Power Systems Applications – DITARTIS and national project PN IV 47PHE/2024.

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